

Synthesis, characterisation and polar effect of the substituent on the reaction mechanism of 3-aminophenyl phosphate esters

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Abstract : The kinetics and mechanism of the acid hydrolysis of 3-aminophenyl phosphate esters have been studied in 0.1 to 6.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl at 90 ± 0.5 °C. The effects of temperature, solvent and substrate concentration on the rate of hydrolysis have been studied and the results suggest that the hydrolysis of monoester occurs by the cleavage of P-O bond fission. The rate coefficients estimated are fairly in good agreement with the experimentally observed ones. Bond fission, molecularity and order of reaction have been supported by Arrhenius parameters, Zucker-Hammett hypothesis, concentration, solvent effect etc.

A study of the reaction in dioxane water mixture suggested the nature of transition state in which charges are developed due to the bimolecular attack of water molecule. Comparative isokinetic rate data of similarly substituted phenyl phosphate monoesters, whose mechanism is known, supported P-O bond fission.

Keywords : Polar effect, reaction mechanism, phosphate esters.

The treatment of phosphate esters as fungicides not only reduces the occurrence of fungi and damage caused by them, but also promotes better growth¹ of plants by incorporation of phosphate residues in form of C-O-P²⁻¹⁰ and C-N-P¹¹⁻²⁷ linkages of more complex biologically important molecules of DNA²⁸ and RNA²⁹. Many organophosphate esters are artificially produced for the practical utility, lubricants³⁰, oil-additives, plasticizers³¹, pesticides³² and are used as antiviral activity³³. Bunton and co-workers⁶ found that acid catalysed hydrolysis occur only when electron attracting substituent was present in the aryl part.

Experimental

3-Aminophenyl phosphate mono ester has been prepared by general method^{34,35} (P. Rudert method).

Phosphorus oxytrichloride (9.0 ml) was added dropwise to a well stirred solution of 3-aminophenol in dry benzene (150 ml) in a round bottom flask under external cooling by (ice-cooled water) with the help of separating funnel about half an hour. After the addition, it was refluxed for about 39 h on the soxhlet heater at constant temperature 65 °C, in order to ensure complete reaction and then distilled at reduced pressure. The first fraction of benzene and unreacted POCl₃ was removed by distillation at *b*₆₀, 120 to 140 °C. It was dissolved in 100 ml

of ice cold water and kept at low temperature overnight, then the 3-aminophenyl phosphorodichloridate converted into 3-aminophenyl dihydrogen phosphate which was extracted with solvent ether, then white coloured crystalline solid was obtained which on recrystallisation from absolute ethyl alcohol gave a white crystalline solid which was identified to be 3-aminophenyl phosphate with the following physical characteristics :

Melting point = 115°C

Percentage	Theoretical	Observed
(i) % of carbon	= 38.09	37.89
(ii) % of hydrogen	= 4.23	4.19
(iii) % of nitrogen	= 7.40	7.20
(iv) % of oxygen	= 33.86	33.72
(v) % of phosphorus	= 16.40	16.32

The infrared spectrum (Fig. 1) of monoester showed the appearance of absorption bands characteristics of :

Substituted aromatic ring	= 765-690 cm ⁻¹
Adjacent-H	= 900-810 cm ⁻¹
O P-OH	= 1170-1080 cm ⁻¹
P-OH	= 1110-1020 cm ⁻¹

O	
-P-	= 1315-1235 cm ⁻¹
C=C-	= 1570-1470 cm ⁻¹
-NH ₂ bending	= 1650-1580 cm ⁻¹
Aromatic ester	= 1720-1635 cm ⁻¹
N-H stretching	= 3450-3380 cm ⁻¹

Above characteristics confirm the structure of 3-aminophenyl phosphate monoester.

Results and discussion

Hydrolysis via conjugate acid species :

Hydrolysis of 3-aminophenyl phosphate monoester has been kinetically studied in 0.1 to 6.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl at 90 ± 0.5 °C. Pseudo-first order rate coefficient have been summarised in Table 1 (Fig. 2), from the result, it may be concluded that the hydrolysis increases with increase in acid molarity.

The rate maxima is arrive at 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl and it gradually decreases with further increase in acid molarity. The rate maxima or bends of pH-log rate profile in acid region have also been found in some other cases^{35,36}. The decrease in the rates from (>4.0 mol

Table 1. pH-log rate profile of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 ± 0.5 °C

HCl (mol dm ⁻³)	pH	10 ⁵ K _c (mol dm min ⁻¹) (Obsd.)	5 + log K _c
6.0	-0.778	47.19	1.67
5.0	-0.699	91.34	1.96
4.0	-0.602	168.73	2.22
3.5	-0.544	160.14	2.20
3.0	-0.477	142.58	2.15
2.5	-0.397	138.81	2.14
2.0	-0.300	123.14	2.09
1.5	-0.176	112.42	2.05
1.0	0.000	97.40	1.98
0.5	0.301	80.61	1.90
0.4	0.400	75.89	1.88
0.3	0.520	68.39	1.83
0.2	0.700	79.11	1.89
0.1	1.000	86.88	1.93
Buffers :	1.24	98.63	1.99
Composition of buffers	2.20	120.02	2.07
	3.30	129.92	2.11
	4.17	135.72	2.13
	5.60	133.09	2.12
	6.43	130.91	2.11
	7.46	128.68	2.10

dm⁻³ HCl) may be due to participation of water molecule, ionic strength effect or both. The decrease in rate

Fig. 1. Infrared spectrum for 3-aminophenyl phosphate monoester.

Fig. 2. pH-log rate profile of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C : (○) experimental rate, (Δ) calculated rate, (□) mono-negative rate

with increase in acidity in the region 0.1 to 0.5 mol dm⁻³ HCl may be attributed to the decrease in concentration of more reactive mononegative species and the incursion of less reactive neutral species. The further rise in rates in the region of 0.1 to 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl may be either due to incursion of conjugate acid species along with neutral species or the negative effect of ionic strength or both. Whether or not the bend in the pH-log rate profile is due to ionic strength effect or water activity, could be determined by carrying out the kinetic runs at constant ionic strength. The rate constant have been summarised in Table 2, Fig. 3, describes a plot between rate constant and acid molarities.

Three linear plots shows the acid catalysed hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at three different ionic strengths (1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 μ).

Linear curves represent the reaction at the specific ionic strength by the following rate equation :

$$K_e = K_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} + C_{H^+} + K_N \quad (1)$$

where K_e , K_{H^+} and C_{H^+} are the observed rate coefficient and specific acid catalysed rate at that ionic strength and concentration of hydrogen ion respectively.

The rate of hydrolysis decreases with increase in ionic strength. The ionic strength effect is subject to the ionic retardation effect or negative salt effect. The corresponding slope values at constant ionic strength 1.0, 2.0 and 3.0 μ are 34.21×10^{-5} , 29.16×10^{-5} and 22.72×10^{-5}

Table 2. Hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at constant ionic strength at 90 °C

Ionic strength (μ) (mol dm ⁻³)	Composition		10 ⁵ K _e (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹) (Obsd.)
	HCl (mol dm ⁻³)	KCl (mol dm ⁻³)	
1.0	0.2	0.8	65.18
1.0	0.4	0.6	72.43
1.0	0.6	0.4	78.54
1.0	0.8	0.2	80.47
1.0	1.0	0.0	97.40
2.0	0.2	1.8	63.63
2.0	0.5	1.5	69.62
2.0	1.0	1.0	85.08
2.0	1.5	0.5	96.44
2.0	1.8	0.2	106.06
2.0	2.0	0.0	123.14
3.0	0.5	2.5	64.46
3.0	1.0	2.0	75.92
3.0	1.5	1.5	85.83
3.0	2.0	1.0	98.04
3.0	2.5	0.5	108.31
3.0	3.0	0.0	142.58

5 mol dm⁻³ min⁻¹, respectively. Fig. 4 shows the specific acid catalysed rates with their logarithmic form at the corresponding ionic strengths. A linear curve is obtained. The slope of this curve represents a constant b_{H^+} , where

Fig. 3. Hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at constant ionic strength at 90 °C : (○) 1.0, (●) 2.0, (⊙) 3.0 μ.

$b' = b/2.303$ and intercepts on the rate axis represents the specific acid catalysed rates ($\log K_{H^+}$). Figs. 4 and 5 describes the relation between log-rate coefficients and ionic strength and Table 3 summarises the log-rate coefficient at that ionic strength.

Table 4 summarises the log-rate coefficients of specific acid catalysed and specific neutral rates at zero ionic strength with their corresponding constants (b'_H and b'_N).

The linearity of the curves of (Figs. 4 and 5) shows the following relation of rate constant with ionic strength. This is an empirical form of Debye-Huckel equation.

$$K = K_0 \exp b \cdot \mu \quad (2)$$

The specific acid catalysed rate may be shown as

$$K_{H^+} = K_{H_0^+} \exp b_{H^+} \cdot \mu \quad (3)$$

and the acid rates are as :

$$K_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} = K_{H_0^+} \cdot C_{H^+} \exp b'_{H^+} \cdot \mu \quad (4)$$

or its logarithmic form can be shown as :

$$5 + \log K_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} = 5 + \log K_{H_0^+} + \log C_{H^+} + b'_{H^+} \cdot \mu \quad (5)$$

where, K_{H^+} , $K_{H_0^+}$, b'_{H^+} and μ are the specific acid catalysed rates at that ionic strength, at zero ionic strength and a constant respectively.

Similarly the specific neutral rates may be represented as follows :

$$K_N = K_{N_0} \exp b_N \cdot \mu \quad (6)$$

and its logarithmic form may be shown as :

$$5 + \log K_N = 5 + \log K_{N_0} + b'_N \cdot \mu \quad (7)$$

where K_N , b'_N and μ are the specific neutral rate, a constant and the ionic strength respectively and $b'_N = b/2.303$.

The eqs. (5) and (7) may be used to compute the acid catalysed and the neutral rates at each experimental rates.

Therefore, the total hydrolysis of 3-aminophenyl phosphate monoester can be represented as :

$$K_e = \text{Acid rates} + \text{Neutral rates} \quad (8)$$

$$K_e = K_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} + K_N$$

where K_e , K_{H^+} , C_{H^+} and K_N are experimental rates, acid catalysed rates and neutral rates respectively.

Table 3. Specific acid catalysed (K_{H^+}) and specific neutral rates (K_{N_0}) for the hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at different ionic strength at 90 °C

Ionic strength	$10^5 K_{H^+}$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹)	$10^5 K_N$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹)	$5 + \log K_{H^+}$	$5 + \log K_N$	$5 + \log K_{N_0}$
1.0	34.21	58.00	1.53	1.76	
2.0	29.16	55.00	1.46	1.74	1.80
3.0	22.72	52.00	1.35	1.71	

Fig. 4. Hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C (log specific neutral rate vs ionic strength)

Fig. 5. Hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C (log specific neutral rate vs ionic strength)

The values of specific acid catalysed rates ($5 + \log K_{H_0}^+ = 1.62$) and specific neutral rates ($5 + \log K_{N_0} = 1.80$) can be obtained from the intercept on the rate axis, while $b'_{H^+} = (-0.039)$ and $b'_N = (-0.0135)$ can be obtained from the slope of (Figs. 4 and 5). Eqs. (5), (7) and (8) have been used to calculate the theoretical rates.

Table 5 summarises both the observed and calculated rates of the hydrolysis in the acid region 0.1 to 4.0 mol dm^{-3} HCl, but beyond 4.0 mol dm^{-3} HCl, there is steep

fall in the rates, which has been presumed due to participation of water molecule as a second reaction partner in the nucleophilic substitution reaction. Thus, the acid catalysed rates can be calculated as :

$$K_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} = K_{H_0}^+ \cdot C_{H^+} \exp b_{H^+} \cdot \mu (a_{H_2O}) \quad (9)$$

or its logarithmic form can be represented as :

$$5 + \log K_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+} = 5 + \log K_{H_0}^+ + \log C_{H^+} + b'_{H^+} \cdot \mu + n \log (a_{H_2O}) \quad (10)$$

Table 4. Specific acid catalysed [$K_{H_0}^+$] and specific neutral [K_{N_0}] rates for the hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at zero ionic strength at 90 °C

$10^5 K_{H_0}^+$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹)	$5 + \log K_{H_0}^+$	b'_{H^+}	$10^5 K_{N_0}$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹)	$5 + \log K_{N_0}$	b'_N
41.68	1.62	-0.039	63.09	1.80	-0.0135

Table 5. Calculated and observed rates for the hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C

HCl (mol dm ⁻³)	pH	$10^5 K_N$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹)	$5 + \log K_N$	$10^5 K_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+}$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹)	$10^5 K_{H^+} \cdot C_{H^+}$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹)	$10^5 K_N$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹)	$10^5 K_e$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹) (Calcd.)	$10^5 K_e$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹) (Obsd.)
1.0	0.000	61.16	1.78	38.10	-	-	99.26	97.40
1.5	-0.176	60.22	1.77	54.63	-	-	114.85	112.42
2.0	-0.300	59.29	1.77	69.66	-	-	128.95	123.14
2.5	-0.397	58.38	1.76	83.08	-	-	141.46	138.81
3.0	-0.477	50.75	1.70	95.49	-	-	146.24	142.68
3.5	-0.544	56.59	1.75	105.68	-	-	162.27	160.14
4.0	-0.602	55.71	1.74	115.87	-	-	171.58	168.73
5.0	-0.699	54.01	1.73	132.73	65.01 *	26.48*	91.49	91.34
6.0	-0.778	52.36	1.71	145.88	33.96*	12.18*	46.14	47.19

$n=0$ for 1.0 to 4.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl and $n^*=2$ and 3 respectively for 5.0 and 6.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl.

Table 6. Hammett plot data for the hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C

HCl (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 K_e$ (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹) (Obsd.)	$5 + \log K_e$	$-H_0$	$-\log (a_{H_2O})$
1.0	97.40	1.98	0.20	0.017
1.5	112.42	2.05	0.47	0.027
2.0	123.14	2.09	0.69	0.039
2.5	138.81	2.14	0.87	0.053
3.0	142.58	2.15	1.05	0.070
3.5	160.14	2.20	1.23	0.087
4.0	168.73	2.22	1.40	0.107
5.0	91.34	1.96	1.76	0.155
6.0	47.19	1.67	2.12	0.211

and neutral rates at higher concentration can be shown as :

$$K_N = K_{N_0} \cdot \exp b_{N \cdot \mu} (a_{H_2O})^n \quad (11)$$

and its logarithmic form can be shown as :

$$5 + \log K_N = 5 + \log K_{N_0} + b'_{N \cdot \mu} + n \log (a_{H_2O}) \quad (12)$$

where (a_{H_2O}) represents water activity parameter.

Molecularity :

The various correlation plots like Hammett plot³⁹ (Figs. 6 and 7) (slope value 0.23), Zucker-Hammett plot⁴⁰ (slope

value 0.79), Bunnett plot (slope value, ω and $\omega^* = 10.00$ and 5.55) and Bunnett-Olsen plot (slope value $\phi = 1.66$) postulates a bimolecular rate of hydrolysis with the involvement of water molecule as a second reaction partner. The slopes of Tables 6 to 8 show the bimolecularity of the reaction.

The Arrhenius parameters⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ at 3.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl; $\Delta E = 18.76$ kcal/mol⁻¹, $\lambda = 2.86 \times 10^6$ s⁻¹, $\Delta S = 31.40$ e.u. and at 5.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl; $\Delta E = 19.67$ kcal/mol⁻¹, $\lambda = 6.36 \times 10^6$ s⁻¹, $\Delta S = 29.81$ e.u.. The above

Fig. 6. Hammett plot for the hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C.

Fig. 7. Zucker-Hammett plot for the hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C.

Arrhenius parameters⁴¹⁻⁴⁴ at 3.0 and 5.0 mol dm⁻³ HCl show the bimolecular mode of hydrolysis with P-O bond fission and by isokinetic relationship plot also suggest the bimolecular hydrolysis with P-O bond fission.

Mechanism :

The mechanism of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate may therefore be formulated as :

Fig. 8. Bunnett plot and old-Bunnett plot for the hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C : (●) $5 + \log K_e - \log C_{H+}$, (○) $5 + \log K_e + H_0$.

Table 7. Zucker-Hammett plot data for the hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C

HCl (mol dm ⁻³)	log C _{H+}	10 ⁵ K _e (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹) (Obsd.)	5 + log K _e
1.0	0.000	97.40	1.98
1.5	0.176	112.42	2.05
2.0	0.300	123.14	2.09
2.5	0.397	138.81	2.14
3.0	0.477	142.58	2.15
3.5	0.544	160.14	2.20
4.0	0.602	168.73	2.22
5.0	0.699	91.34	1.96
6.0	0.778	47.19	1.67

Table 8. Bunnett and Bunnett-Olsen plot data for the hydrolysis of mono-3-aminophenyl phosphate at 90 °C

HCl (mol dm ⁻³)	log C _{H+}	10 ⁵ K _e (mol dm ⁻³ min ⁻¹) (Obsd.)	5 + log K _e	-H ₀	5 + log K _e - log C _{H+}	5 + log K _e + H ₀	-(-log C _{H+} + H ₀)	-log (a _{H2O})
	(a)	(b)	(c)	(d)	(e)	(f)	(g)	(h)
1.0	0.000	97.40	1.98	0.20	1.98	1.78	0.20	0.017
2.0	0.300	123.14	2.09	0.69	1.78	1.40	0.39	0.039
2.5	0.397	138.81	2.14	0.87	1.74	1.27	0.47	0.053
3.0	0.477	142.58	2.15	1.05	1.67	1.10	0.57	0.070
3.5	0.544	160.14	2.20	1.23	1.65	0.97	0.68	0.087
4.0	0.602	168.73	2.22	1.40	1.61	0.82	0.79	0.107
5.0	0.699	91.34	1.96	1.76	1.26	0.20	1.06	0.155
6.0	0.778	47.19	1.67	2.12	0.89	-0.45	1.34	0.211

(a) Formation of conjugate acid species by fast pre-equilibrium proton transfer from the un-dissociated monoesters :

(b) Bimolecular nucleophilic attack of water on phosphorus via conjugate acid species of the monoester involving P-O bond fission S_N² (P) :

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